

Sound identification key for biological sounds below 2 kHz based on spectrograms (FFT = 256, sampling frequency = 4 kHz) from mesophotic reefs in French Polynesia

Xavier Raick, xavier.raick@uliege.be

1	The frequency of the sound is not constant along time, i.e., the sound is frequency modulated.....	2
1'	The frequency of the sound is constant along time or the variations are very small.....	57
2	The frequency modulation presents patterns (repetition of cycles).....	3
2'	The frequency modulation does not present patterns (no repetition of cycles).....	9
3	Peak(s) are visible on the spectrogram.....	4
3'	No peak(s) are visible on the spectrogram.....	6
4	The difference of frequency between the beginning (F_{beg}) of the sound and the end (F_{end}) of the sound is higher than 100 Hz ($F_{\text{beg}} - F_{\text{end}} > 100$ Hz).....	5
4'	The difference of frequency between the beginning of the sound (F_{beg}) and the end (F_{end}) of the sound is smaller than 100 Hz ($F_{\text{beg}} - F_{\text{end}} < 100$ Hz).....	CS1
5	One peak is visible on the spectrogram.....	CS1 (variant)
5'	Two peaks and one downsweep are visible on the spectrogram.....	CS1 (variant)
6	Whale vocalization (typically longer than 1 s).....	whale
6'	Not a whale vocalization.....	7
7	Bandwidth greater than 600 Hz.....	CS2
7'	Fish sound with a bandwidth < 600 Hz.....	8
8	The sound consists of (pseudo)harmonics and all the frequencies are below 1 kHz. The sound is made of 3 to 6 frequency modulations with temporal discontinuities (i.e., short intervals of time between each modulation).....	AS3/DS3/US3
8'	The sound does not consist of (pseudo)harmonics and is made of two convex modulations (a convex modulation = with a convace hypograph).....	sound of unknown origin
9	An inflexion point (i.e., a point at which the curve changes from being concave to convex or vice versa) is visible.....	18
9'	No inflexion point is visible.....	10
10	There is one(s) clear turning(s) point(s) (i.e., a point at which the sign of the curve changes sign): the sound is made of a downsweep and an upsweep part.....	11
10'	There is not clear turning point: the sign is only a downsweep or only an upsweep.....	20

11	Odontocete call.....	odontocete
11'	Different from above.....	12
12	The signal resembles a concave function (= with a convex hypograph).....	13
12'	The signal resembles a convex function (= with a convace hypograph).....	17
13	The entire sound is above 1 kHz..... sound of unknown origin with a 'hill' form on the spectrogram	
13'	The entire sound is under 1 kHz.....	14
14	The sound is flat except at the beginning and at the end. When the harmonic(s) is(are) visible(s), it(they) tend(s) to have a more pronounced downsweep aspect than H ₀ CS3 (see also CS4)	
14'	Different from above.....	15
15	The sound is similar to CS3 but the more pronounced downsweep aspect is not observed..... CS4 (see also CS3)	
15'	Different from above.....	16
16	The sound is shorter than 0.5 s..... CS5 (see also CS4 and CS6)	
16'	Different from above.....	generally a whale vocalization
17	The entire sound is above 1 kHz..... sound of unknown origin with a 'valley' form on the spectrogram	
17'	Whale sound, generally under 400 Hz.....	whale
18	Odontocete call.....	odontocete
18'	Different from above.....	19
19	The sound is a harmonic FM sound made of two different parts: a concave-function part followed by a convex-function part. Additional harmonics are visible in the convex part compared to the concave part. The dominant frequency is always below 1 kHz. The second part can have a flat / upsweeping aspect or a flat / downsweeping aspect. Aurally, it looks like a donkey's bray..... CS6	
19'	Different from above.....	not considered
20	Upsweep.....	21
20'	Downsweep.....	37
21	The sound has two upsweeps.....	rare fish sound, not used in the analysis
21'	The sound does not have two upsweeps.....	22

22	Peak(s) is(are) visible(s) on the spectrogram.....	23
22'	No peak(s) is visible on the spectrogram.....	24
23	The peak frequency is below 400 Hz.....	US1 (variant)
23'	The sound presents a 'pulsed aspect' and consist of (pseudo)harmonics. The peak frequency is above 400 Hz and the ΔF between two consecutives harmonics is around 220 Hz. This sound can have a US or a DS aspect.....	DS/US9
24	The peak frequency is higher than 800 Hz and the bandwidth is shorter than 200 Hz.....	25
24'	Different from above.....	26
25	'Fast pulse train' aspect.....	high-frequency US sound with an FPT aspect produced by odontocetes
25'	No 'fast pulse train' aspect.....	high-frequency US sound produced by odontocetes
26	(Pseudo)harmonics are visible on the spectrogram.....	27
26'	No (pseudo)harmonics are visible on the spectrogram.....	31
27	The frequency band between two (pseudo)harmonics is greater than 180 Hz.....	29
27'	Different from above.....	28
28	The peak frequency is below 300 Hz.....	US1
28'	The peak frequency is above 300 Hz.....	US4
29	The sound presents a 'pulsed aspect' and consist of (pseudo)harmonics. The peak frequency is above 400 Hz and the ΔF between two consecutives harmonics is around 220 Hz. This sound can have a US or a DS aspect.....	DS/US9
29'	The sound does not have a 'pulsed aspect'.....	30
30	The fundamental frequency appears as longer than the (pseudo)harmonics.....	US3 (see also DS3 and AS3)
30'	Different from above.....	US2
31	The sound is long and irregular (with 'accidents') with no frequencies bellow 400 Hz.....	whale
31'	Different from above.....	32
32	Fast pulse train aspect.....rare low frequency US sound with an FPT aspect produced by fish, not used in the analysis
32'	No 'fast pulse train' aspect.....	33

33	Quick increase in frequency (sounds peculiar).....	34
33'	Different from above.....	36
34	The sound duration is under 0.15 s. The frequency modulation is so fast that it appears vertical and it sound like a 'bubble bursting'.....	sound of unknown origin
34'	Different from above.....	35
35	Peak frequency higher than 800 Hz.....	fast US sound produced by whales
35'	Peak frequency lower than 700 Hz.....	low-frequency fast US sound produced by whales
36	All the sound is above 200 Hz.....	low-frequency US sound produced by whales
36'	Different from above.....	not considered
37	The sound contains more than one downsweep.....	38
37'	The sound only contains one downsweep.....	43
38	The sound contains at least three downsweeps.....	39
38'	The sound does not contain more than two downsweeps.....	42
39	The sound only contains three downsweeps and is followed by at least one peak.....	DS8 (variant)
39'	Different from above.....	40
40	There is more than one main frequency zone in the spectrogram.....	consecutive DS1s
40'	Different from above.....	41
41	All the sound is above 200 Hz.....	rare fish sound made of several DSs, not used in the analysis
41'	Different from above..	rare very-low frequency fish sound made of several DSs, not used in the analysis
42	The sound is made of at least 3 (pseudo)harmonics...rare DS fish sound, not used in the analysis	
42'	different from above.....	44
43	Peak(s) are visible on the spectrogram.....	DS8
43'	No peaks are visible on the spectrogram.....	DS7
44	Odontocete DS sound (the peak frequency is generally higher than 900 Hz).....	odontocete
44'	The peak frequency is lower than 900 Hz.....	45

45	The sound has at least two (pseudo)harmonics.....	46
45'	Different from above.....	54
46	The ΔF between two consecutives (pseudo)harmonics is greater than 100-120 Hz.....	49
46'	The ΔF between two consecutives (pseudo)harmonics is smaller than 100-120 Hz.....	47
47	The sound has a 'pulsed aspect' throughout the downsweep.....	DS6
47'	Different from above.....	48
48	The peak frequency is higher than 400 Hz.....	DS2
48'	The peak frequency is lower than 400 Hz.....	DS5
49	Peak(s) is (are) visible(s) and/or the entire or a portion of the sound has a 'pulsed aspect'.....	52
49'	Different from above.....	50
50	The sound has a frequency downsweep with a high slope and has frequencies bellow 400 Hz.....	51
50'	Different from above.....	DS10
51	Harmonics have such a strong inclination that the sound appears almost as a single peak.....	DS11
51'	Different from above.....	DS3 (see also US3 and AS3)
52	The peak frequency is above 400 Hz.....	DS/US9
52'	The peak frequency is under 400 Hz.....	53
53	Peaks are visible after the end of a short frequency downsweep.....	DS12
53'	Peak(s) are visible(s) during the beginning of the frequency downsweep. This 'pulsed start' usually appears at the beginning of the sound. The slope of the frequency downsweep decreases over time and some harmonics may end up flat.....	DS13
54	The duration is generally longer than 0.5 s, the sound is irregular.....	DS sound produced by whales
54'	Different from above.....	55
55	The peak frequency is lower than 200 Hz.....	low-frequency DS sound of unknown origin
55'	The peak frequency is higher than 200 Hz.....	56

56	The sound has a pulsed aspect.....rare DS fish sound with a FPT aspect, not used in the analysis	
56'	Different from above.....	DS1 (DS)
57	Peak(s) are visible on the spectrogram.....	58
57'	Different from above.....	113
58	The sound is a pulse series made of two parts. The first part is tonal and downsweeping while the second part is longer and is not tonal.....rare fish sound, not used in the analyses	
58'	Different from above.....	59
59	More than one peak is visible on the spectrogram.....	60
59'	Only one peak is visible on the spectrogram.....	not considered
60	Two peaks are visible on the spectrogram.....	61
60'	More than two peaks are visible on the spectrogram.....	63
61	The sound is made of two broadband (bandwidth >1 kHz) peaks with the same intensity.....	62
61'	The sound is made of two peaks with frequential discontinuities.....	not considered
62	The period is between 60 and 120 ms.....	2P
62'	The period is between 120 and 180 ms.....	2P (variant)
63	Three peaks are visible on the spectrogram.....	64
63'	More than three peaks are visible on the spectrogram.....	68
64	The peak period is regular.....	65
64'	The peak period is not regular.....	not considered
65	The peak frequency is below 200 Hz.....	PS4
65'	The peak frequency is higher than 200 Hz.....	66
66	In the sound, there are frequencies bellow 400 Hz.....	67
66'	In the sound, there are no frequencies bellow 400 Hz.....	PS5
67	The period is longer than 0.18 s.....	PS3bis
67'	Different from above.....	PS3

68	The peak period is regular through all the sound or the sound is made of two parts with a regular period within each part.....	69
68'	The peak period is not regular through all the sound (it can increase, decrease or have no pattern)....	74
69	The first peak of the sound is more intense and presents frequential discontinuities compared to the following ones. The first period is usually twice as long as the period of the rest of the sound and the first particular peak is followed by a regular pulse series.....	70
69'	Different from above.....	72
70	The period within the regular pulse series is longer than 60 ms.....	71
70'	The period of the regular pulse series is a 'fast pulse train', i.e., the pulse period is usually between 10 and 50 ms.....	FPT8
71	The regular part is made of 3 to 6 pulses.....	PS18
71'	The regular part is made of more than 6 pulses.....	PS18 (rare variant, not used in the analysis)
72	The pulse period is constant throughout the entire sound.....	81
72'	The pulse period is not constant throughout the sound: the sound is divided in a first part with a short pulse period and a second part with a longer pulse period, or vice versa.....	73
73	The sound is made of two parts. The pulse period within the first part is shorter than within the second part.....	FPT-PS (see also PS10 and FPT2)
73'	The sound is made of two parts. The pulse period within the first part is longer than within the second part.....	rare fish sound, not used in the analysis
74	The spectrogram has frequential discontinuities or different frequencies appear in the spectrogram...	75
74'	The spectrogram is continuous along all the frequencies of the sound.....	77
75	The bandwidth is larger than 1 kHz and the sound has frequencies above 1.3 kHz.....	rare high frequency fish sound, not used in the analysis
75'	Different from above.....	76
76	The bandwidth is larger than 0.5 kHz and the sound has frequencies above 600 Hz.....	PS19
76'	Different from above.....	rare high-frequency fish sound, not used in the analysis
77	The period increases with time.....	78
77'	Different from above.....	79

78	The first period is around 0.03 s and the peak frequency is between 250 and 300 Hz.....	PS13
78'	Different from above.....	PS7
79	Sound hardly audible, bad signal-noise ratio.....	not considered
79'	Different from above.....	80
80	The bandwidth is usually between 0.3 and 1.8 kHz.....	PS14
80'	The bandwidth is usually between 0 and 1.2 kHz.....	PS15
81	The peak period is longer than 0.75 s.....	82
81'	The peak period is shorter than 0.75 s.....	83
82	The peak frequency is higher than 1 kHz.....	SPS2
82'	The peak frequency is lower than 1 kHz.....	SPS1 (previously known as SPS)
83	The sound is a 'fast pulse train', i.e. the pulse period is usually between 10 and 50 ms.....	84
83'	The sound is not a 'fast pulse train', i.e., the pulse period is longer than 60 ms.....	97
84	There is more than 4 consecutive 'fast pulse trains'. In addition, their length diminished with time. Two frequencies peaks are visible in the spectrogram.....	
rare fish sound made of stereotyped fast pulse trains, not used in the analysis	
84'	Different from above.....	85
85	There is more than one fast pulse train sound.....	rare fish sound made of two consecutive FPT7
85'	Different from above.....	86
86	There are frequencies above 2 kHz. The peak frequency of the sound is usually above 600 Hz.....	87
86'	There are not frequencies above 2 kHz.....	88
87	Duration longer than 0.5 s.....	high frequency clicks produced by odontocetes
87'	Duration shorter than 0.5 s.....	FPT7
88	Duration longer than 0.25 s.....	89
88'	Duration shorter than 0.25 s.....	91
89	Bandwidth higher than 500 Hz.....	FPT1
89'	Bandwidth shorter than 500 Hz.....	90

90	The sound has frequential discontinuities in the spectrogram.....	FPT9
90'	Different from above.....	FPT2
91	All the frequencies in the sound are under 700 Hz and the peak frequency is usually under 400 Hz.....	FPT4
91'	Different from above.....	92
92	The sound is above 700 Hz and the bandwidth is usually shorter than 500 Hz.....	FPT5 (see others FPTs)
92'	Different from above.....	93
93	The bandwidth of the sound is usually between 0 and 1 kHz and the peak frequency is above 400 Hz.....	FPT3
93'	Bandwidth usually between 0.2 and 1.8 kHz.....	94
94	Different frequencies appear in the spectrogram. The peak frequency is around 1 kHz and the sound usually does not appear alone.....	FPT10
94'	Different from above.....	95
95	The bandwidth of the sound is usually larger than 600 Hz.....	96
95'	The bandwidth of the sound is usually smaller than 600 Hz and the peak frequency is around 500 Hz. These sounds usually do not appear alone.....	FPT11 (variant, see FPT11, AS4, and AS5)
96	The sound usually has one main frequential discontinuity: two frequency peaks are visible in the spectrogram (one around 500 Hz and the other one around 1.25 kHz).....	FPT11
96'	Different from above.....	FPT6
97	The sound has a period shorter than 0.10 s and contains at least 15 peaks.....	98
97'	Different from above.....	100
98	The sound contains only frequencies under 600 Hz.....	PS10
98'	Different from above.....	99
99	The sound contains frequencies above 1 – 1.2 kHz.....	PS11 (not to confound with dolphin's clicks)
99'	Different from above.....	PS9
100	Period usually shorter than 0.15 s.....	105
100'	Period usually longer than 0.20 s.....	101

101	The sound contains at least 13 peaks.....	102
101'	The sound contains less than 13 peaks.....	103
102	The peak frequency is above 300 Hz.....	PS6
102'	The peak frequency is under 300 Hz.....	PS20
103	The sound contains only frequencies above 1.2 kHz.....	PS21
103'	Different from above.....	104
104	Peak frequency around 165 Hz, between 8 and 9 pulses, bandwidth smaller than 55 Hz.....not considered (previously known as PS8)	
104'	Different from above.....	PS12
105	Only frequencies above 1 kHz.....	PS22 (previously known as high frequency fast pulse series)
105'	Different from above.....	106
106	Only frequencies under 600 Hz.....	108
106'	Different from above.....	107
107	The peak frequency diminishes with time, all the sound is between 0.6 and 1.4 kHz. The sound contains 5 to 8 pulses and sound like 'a bird song'.....	112
107'	Different from above.....	110
108	Pulses present 1 to 3 high-energy levels. The lowest one is the most intense and the peak frequency is around 150 Hz. These types of low pulse series sound lower than others low fast PS.....	109
108'	The sound is a low fast PS but different from above.....	PS17
109	The sound contains 4 pulses.....	PS23
109'	The sound contains more than 4 pulses.....	PS23 (variant)
110	Usually short pulse period (around 81 ms), peak frequency around 750 Hz.....	PS2
110'	Different from above.....	111
111	Peak frequency above 0.4 kHz. This sound is usually stereotyped and more intense than other PSs. Different frequencies appear in the spectrogram 'like a barcode'.....PS16 (variant, previously known as PS1)	
111'	The sound has a pulse period around 120 ms.....	PS16

112	The sound is followed by spaced peaks.....	DS4 (variant)
112'	The sound is not followed by spaced peaks.....	DS4
113	The sound has at least 3 (pseudo)harmonics.....	114
113'	Different from above.....	125
114	The peak frequency is below 0.5 kHz and all the frequencies in the sound are under 0.7 kHz.....	115
114'	Different from above.....	118
115	H_0 is usually more intense and the sound has a 'pulsed aspect'. The ΔF between two consecutive harmonics is around 50 Hz.....	AS8
115'	Different from above.....	116
116	H_0 is more intense and longer than the harmonics. The ΔF between two consecutive harmonics is around 70 Hz.....	AS2
116'	Different from above.....	117
117	All the frequencies are between 100 and 600 Hz. There are 3 to 4 clear harmonics. The ΔF between two consecutive harmonics is around 140 Hz.....AS3 (see also DS3 and US3; and see also CS4 if ΔF is higher)	
117'	Different from above.....	AS1
118	The ΔF between two consecutive harmonics is greater than 110 Hz.....	119
118'	Different from above.....	120
119	The ΔF between two consecutive harmonics is higher than 300 Hz.....AS9 (previously named 'rare harmonic AS fish sound')	
119'	The ΔF between two consecutive harmonics is around 140 Hz. Only some harmonics appears completely flat in the spectrogram.....	AS3 (variant)
120	Longer than 0.4 s and there are frequencies below 400 Hz. The sound has a 'pulsed aspect'.....AS10 (previously named 'rare low-frequency AS fish sound with a 'pulsed aspect'')	
120'	Different from above.....	121
121	The peak frequency is above 900 Hz.....	122
121'	The peak frequency is under 900 Hz.....	123
122	The duration of the sound is shorter than 125 ms and the bandwidth is greater than 500 Hz.....	AS11
122'	Different from above.....	AS4 = kwa-like

123	The ΔF between two harmonics is smaller than the ΔF of one harmonics.....	AS6/7
123'	Different from above.....	124
124	The duration of the sound is shorter than 125 ms and the bandwidth is greater than 400 Hz.....	AS12
124'	Different from above.....	AS5
125	On the spectrogram, only one flat energetic zone is visible.....	126
125'	On the spectrogram, two flat energetic zone are visible.....	130
126	'Coma' shape.....	sound of unknown origin
126'	Different from above.....	128
127	Peak frequency bellow 100 Hz. The fundamental frequency is longer in duration compared to the higher harmonics.....	AS2 (variant)
127'	Different from above.....	128
128	Longer than 0.5 s.....	129
128'	Different from above.....	sound of unknown origin that appears 'flat' on the spectrogram
129	Shorter than 2 s.....	sound of unknow origin
129'	Longer than 2 s. The frequency of the sound is not exactly 100% constant. Irregularities are usually observed at the beginning.....	whale
130	There are two zones at different frequencies and flat.....	whale (but see also CS3 and CS5)
130'	Different from above.....	sound of unknow origin that appears as a 'stair' in the spectrogram